

Tudi

Experiment in Research Institute of Mountain Stockbreeding and Agriculture of Troyan First experiment

07 June 2024

Prof. Martin Banov, Phd, Prof. Dimitre Nikolov, Phd, Prof. I. Boevsky, Phd, assist. prof.
Krasimir Kostenarov, Phd, and assist. prof. EkatherinaTzvetanova, Phd

New Bulgarian University

TUdi

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action under grant agreement No 101000224.

Results of the first experiments Chelopechene district test field

The research in the Research Institute of Mountain Stockbreeding and Agriculture of Troyan included the observance of the impact of annual fertilizing with organic fertilizers on the productive and qualitative indicators of natural grassland in the conditions of the Central Balkan Mountain.

The experiment was set on a natural meadow of *Chrysopogon gryllus* - *Agrostis capillaris* type in the central part of the Central Balkan Mountains, using the block design (in 4 replications) with a 25 m² plot size. The soils in the region are pseudopodzolic (*Planosols*) with very low natural fertility (1-1.5% humus with a predominant share of fulvic acids). The total nitrogen amount was low (0.10-0.12%) with pH_{KCl} = 4.2-4.6. Acidity affects the soil's ability to retain nutrients. Acidic soils (in particular) bind phosphorus and some trace elements (including Mo), which improve nitrogen fixation. Soil acidity is primarily due to exchangeable aluminum (Al). The lowest amount of this element is found in the lower part of the pseudopodzolic horizon and the uppermost part of the illuvial, i.e., where waterlogging and oxidation-reduction processes are most pronounced.

Variants of the research

1. Control (no fertilizing) – (C);
2. Foliar feeding by Biostim (5 l/ha dose) – (Biostim);
3. Foliar feeding by Biostim (6 l/ha dose) and Boron humate (dose of 1.8 l/ha) – (Biostim + BH);
4. Foliar feeding by Biostim (7 l/ha doze) and Molybdenum humate (2 l/ha doze) – (Biostim + MH);
5. Foliar feeding by Biostim (8.6 l/ha doze) and Phosphorus humate (4 l/ha dose) – (Biostim + PH);

Productivity of a natural meadow of *Chrysopogon gryllus* - *Agrostis capillaris*

Bio-fertilization did not significantly affect productivity in the natural meadow In the first experimental year. The realized yield in the bio-fertilization variants was higher compared to the untreated control but without a statistically significant difference. The

highest yield of fresh (1720.0 kd/da) and dry (598,0 kd/da) mass were found in the grasslands treated with Biostim and Molybdenum humate, followed by the variants with independently Biostim and combined application of Biostim with Phosphorus humate.

Table 1. Yield of fresh and dry matter (kd/da) of a natural meadow of *Chrysopogon gryllus-Agrostis capillaris* type

Variants	Fresh mass		Dry mass	
	kd/da	%	kd/da	%
C	1390.0	100.0	482.0	100.0
Biostim	1690.0	121.6	527.0	109.3
Biostim + BH	1420.0	102.2	507.0	105.2
Biostim + MH	1720.0	123.7	598.0	124.1
Biostim + PH	1550.0	111.5	539.0	111.8

The analyzed data show the lowest productivity in the variants with foliar feeding by Biostim + Boron humate. The difference was 300.0 kd/da (for the fresh mass) and 91.0 kd/da (for the dry mass) compared to the maximum values of fresh and dry mass, respectively for the options with organic fertilizers.

Botanical composition of a natural meadow of *Chrysopogon gryllus - Agrostis capillaris* type

We applied organic materials with a complex action and a high content of labile humic substances to perform a corrective function in the integrated "soil-plant" system. Methodical and regulated fertilizing created conditions for changes in the phytocenological and qualitative profile of the natural grassland.

Grasses in the treated variants occupied a smaller share in the composition of the grass matter compared to those in the control. In 2022, the species with a predominant share in the grassland of the natural meadow are *Agrostis capillaris*, *Bothriochloa ischaemum*, *Chrysopogon gryllus* and *Festuca ovina*. In the foliar feeding variants, *Agrostis capillaris* (from 0.2% to 3.6%) and *Chrysopogon gryllus* (from 1.9% to 8.7%) increased their percentage compared to the control. In contrast, the applied agrotechnical measure led to a reduction in the relative share of *Bothriochloa ischaemum* (from 2.3% to 8.2%) and the appearance of the *Festuca ovina* species (1.3% in the variant - Biostim + PH).

Figure 1. Botanical composition of a natural meadow of *Chrysopogon gryllus* - *Agrostis capillaris* type

From the representatives of the *Fabaceae* family - *Trifolium campestre* is present in the natural grassland in all studied variants. The relative share of the species varied from 0.6% (C) to 4.2% (Biostim + BH). *Lotus corniculatus* was also observed in the variants with foliar organic fertilizers. The forage crop has a high productive potential and good adaptability to environmental conditions. Its share in the grassland in the first experimental year was from 3.4% (Biostim) to 5.7% (Biostim + BH). The results indicate that the combined treatment of Biostim with Boron humate stimulates to the highest degree the growth and development of legume forages, which is a prerequisite for obtaining forage mass with higher quality and nutritional value.

Natural meadows and rangeland resources are preferred in ruminant raising in mountain regions, as they are low-cost and nature-friendly.

Figure 2. The main chemical composition (%) of a natural meadow of *Chrysopogon gryllus* - *Agrostis capillaris* type

Applied technologies increased the efficiency factor when using plant nutrients, improving their photosynthetic activity, and nitrogen and carbohydrate metabolism. The effectiveness of foliar bio-fertilization with Biostim and humate fertilizers is also expressed in increasing the content of crude protein and calcium from 1.57% to 3.41% and from 0.90% to 1.55%, respectively. The content of the carbohydrate fraction in the dry matter varied from 33.82% (C) to 34.20% (Biostim + MH). A decrease in crude fiber values from 1.83% (Biostim) to 3.85% (Biostim + PH) was reported.

The results show that the treatment of the grassland in a natural meadow of *Chrysopogon gryllus* - *Agrostis capillaris* type, with the tested combinations, had a positive effect on the productivity, floristic composition, and quality of the grass mass.